

Mapping with, not just for, nature: Exploring the implications of more-than-human participatory mapping for environmental stewardship

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ABSTRACT

Environmental decision-making remains limited by methods that privilege human values and struggle to account for more-than-human interests. This study explores whether participatory mapping can address this gap. Using transect-walk interviews and digital mapping with 28 participants along Mission Creek, we examine how we can attempt to spatialize non-human lives and relationships. Although participants struggled to translate dynamic multispecies processes into cartographic form, the mapping process fostered relational awareness and multinaturalistic understanding. We argue that more-than-human participatory mapping can complement ecosystem-services approaches by cultivating adaptive, reflexive, and multispecies-attentive forms of environmental stewardship.

1. Introduction

Contemporary environmental crises - massive biodiversity losses, widespread pollution, and anthropogenic climate change - have become impossible to ignore (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2023). These crises reveal the limits of human-centric governance that have historically shaped environmental policy (Rockström et al., 2020). Environmental crises are both physical and epistemological, arising from the persistent separation of nature and society that positions human wellbeing as distinct from, rather than dependent upon, the environment (Latour, 1993; Plumwood, 2002). Despite greater awareness of socio-ecological interdependence, most frameworks continue to treat non-humans as background rather than co-constituents of shared environments.

More-than-human geography addresses this fracture by representing the historically excluded agencies and “voices” of non-humans (Houston et al., 2018; Whatmore, 2017). More-than-humans encompass living beings and entities such as plants, animals, fungi, rivers, and mountains (Whatmore, 2006). It emphasizes relational ontologies that challenge human exceptionalism and highlight the co-production of socio-ecological worlds (Lorimer & Hodgetts,

2024). However, translating these ideas into decision-making remains challenging (De Grandpré & Corbett, 2025).

Participatory mapping, long used to enable communities to represent their spatial knowledge and map what matters to them (Chambers, 2006; Harley, 1987), may offer one pathway to bridge theory and practice. However, mapping more-than-human interests presents a representational challenge – since we cannot speak to non-humans, can we speak for them? The potential of participatory mapping, therefore, lies less in direct representation and more in fostering what Lorimer and Hodgetts (2024) call multinaturalistic awareness - recognizing that multiple, coexisting worldviews of nature offer different but equally valid insights into shared environments and their inhabitants.

This paper builds on earlier work that examined the representational challenges of “speaking” for more-than-humans in participatory mapping (De Grandpré & Corbett, 2025). It examines how the act of mapping more-than-human worlds shapes participants’ ethical awareness, reflexivity, and understanding of socio-ecological relations, and how this may influence environmental decision-making and stewardship. To explore how participatory mapping functions as a relational practice, we ask: (1) how do participants navigate the limits of mapping dynamic, more-than-human processes; (2) what forms of relational or ethical awareness emerge through trying to map more-than-human interests; and (3) how might mapping more-than-human interests inform inclusive and adaptive approaches to environmental stewardship?

2. Methodology and Methods

This research builds on qualitative fieldwork along Mission Creek in Kelowna, BC, drawing on the same dataset as De Grandpre & Corbett (2025), with complementary but distinct findings. It explores how participatory mapping can serve as a relational practice that cultivates ethical attentiveness to more-than-human interests and informs inclusive and adaptive environmental stewardship. We build on participatory mapping research focused on representation and inclusion (e.g., Chambers, 2006; Cronkleton et al., 2010; Reyes-García et al., 2012) to explore the representation of more-than-human interests. Rather than emphasizing cartographic precision, this research focuses on the relational aspects of mapping that extend “community” beyond humans. This study does not assess institutional uptake or policy outcomes. This study’s contributions are conceptual and exploratory rather than evaluative.

2.1 Study Area

Mission Creek contributes one-quarter of the inflow into Okanagan Lake (Shepherd et al., 2006). It flows from the Monashee Mountains through forested, agricultural, and urban landscapes, providing critical habitat for species including kokanee salmon, black cottonwoods, and endangered species such as the western screech owl and painted turtle (Eyjolfson & Enns, 2017). It also underpins the regional water supply and tourism (Statistics Canada, 2022). Mission Creek holds cultural and spiritual significance for the Syilx Okanagan Peoples, who have long used it as traditional fishing grounds and whose traditional practices recognize *siwłk^w*—the living water—as a relative and source of law and responsibility (ONA, 2021). These ecological and cultural dimensions make Mission Creek an important site to explore tensions between human and more-than-human interests.

2.2 Data Collection

Twenty-eight participants were selected through purposive and snowball sampling to capture diversity of relationships with Mission Creek, rather than to achieve representativeness of the population. This sample size is appropriate for in-depth, qualitative analysis focused on meaning-making within participatory mapping (Guest et al., 2006; Chambers, 2006). Participants were intentionally selected to represent multiple forms of knowledge, from technical and governance-related to experiential, sensory, and cultural. This allowed the study to consider how different epistemic positions shape attempts to engage with more-than-human interests. Participants included scientists, conservationists, landowners, business owners, farmers, foresters, recreators, and representatives from land trusts, irrigation districts, and local/regional/Syilx government. The data were gathered using two methods:

1. Transect walk interviews: Participants took part in a semi-structured “moving interview” while walking along sections of the creek, narrating ecological observations, memories, and multispecies encounters.
2. Chauffeured digital mapping sessions: Participants answered the semi-structured interview questions in interviews and focus groups, using ArcGIS Survey123 to locate features corresponding to more-than-human interests or their reflections.

2.2 Analysis

All interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and thematically analyzed in NVivo using an inductive coding approach informed by grounded theory. Primary codes included: representational limits (non-stable state vs fixed mapping, temporal change, scale mismatch), more-than-human agency, hesitation/epistemic uncertainty about speaking for non-humans, relational awareness and care (affective responses, reciprocity, responsibility), and multinaturalism/knowledge pluralism. The analysis focused on how participants interpreted non-human agency, expressed care, and negotiated their ability to speak for more-than-humans. Particular attention was given to moments of uncertainty and hesitation, where participants struggled to describe or spatialize non-human interests, revealing limits of mapping.

Following the findings of previous research (De Grandpré & Corbett, 2025), we recognize that there are representational gaps when recording non-human voices. This project, therefore, treats participatory mapping not as a neutral tool but as a relational practice that uncovers the gaps and ethical tensions.

3. Results

The findings suggest that participatory mapping may function as a preparatory practice that shapes how values, uncertainties, and trade-offs are understood and articulated in environmental decision-making. Participants highlighted the difficulty of translating more-than-human interests into cartographic form due to their complexity. This finding underscores the challenge of representing dynamic and relational socio-ecological processes. Furthermore, the process of mapping, rather than the final map itself, proved to be more important by providing space to enhance relational awareness and ethical reflection. This insight emphasizes the value of

engaging with more-than-human entanglements rather than focusing solely on cartographic representation.

3.1 The Limits of Translation

The attempts of participants to spatialize more-than-human interests revealed both practical and philosophical limits. Participants hesitated to locate more-than-human interests, questioning if it was possible to represent them with a point, line, or polygon. One participant noted, “You can’t really put a pin where the salmon are. It changes every year, and the whole river is part of that story.” Others noted that habitats and socio-ecological relationships are continuously shifting, while mapping demands fixed boundaries. To represent the riparian zone, as one participant explained, “...you’d have to shade half the valley for it to make sense – it’s always changing with floods, beavers, and plant growth.”

Temporal limits also surfaced. Maps freeze time, while ecological relations unfold through seasons and generations. As one participant reflects, “it feels strange to box in the creek when it’s always moving, always reshaping itself.” Others struggled to compress interdependent processes, such as the relationship between salmon and cottonwood trees, into fixed symbols. This surfaces how cartography’s fixed syntax often clashes with the fluid and relational nature of socio-ecological systems (Country et al., 2015).

These representational limits reveal that participatory mapping, while valuable, risks flattening ecological complexity and reproducing the logics of control that more-than-human geography seeks to unsettle (Whatmore, 2006). However, tensions of representation may be productive. Struggling to map seemingly unmappable phenomena prompted participants to consider the limits of representation and fostered humility and attentiveness to relational complexity.

3.2 Relational Awareness and Multinaturalism

During the mapping process, participant observations shifted from describing where more-than-human live to describing how their lives intertwine. Scientists and conservationists emphasized keystone species and measurable indicators of ecological well-being, such as sedimentation or spawning areas. Untrained experts, including farmers, recreationalists, and residents, focused on sensory and emotional connections. As one participant suggests, “...Mission Creek runs through all of society. It is a critical place where people can go to witness and connect with nature. It’s somewhere where I can connect to the rhythms of nature, like the salmon through life and death, their spawning and dying cycle.” Together, these observations generated a multinaturalistic awareness of Mission Creek that explicitly recognizes that multiple ontologies of nature coexist, are equally valuable, and enrich understanding (Lorimer & Hodgetts, 2024).

As the interviews progressed, many participants described Mission Creek as a co-creator of the landscape, rather than a managed object. One participant noted that “we’ve spent decades trying to contain [the river], but it keeps reminding us that it’s a system, not a line on a map.” Other participants described a river as an agent in the human community’s well-being. One reflects on the effects of climate change linking human and ecological health, “When the creek floods, everyone panics – but when it dries up, nobody talks about it. But it’s a sign that something’s off for all of us.”

Observing or reflecting on the creek often led to realizations about responsibility and reciprocity, cultivating attentiveness and care towards more-than-humans in shared spaces. Across many interviews, emotional responses such as grief, guilt, and hope emerged when reflecting on anthropogenic impacts on the ecosystem. “You can see on the map where the creek breathes and where we’ve taken that breath away,” a participant noted. Another reflected, “I used to worry about flooding because of my house... Now I think maybe the creek has been the one drowning.” Such reflections surfaced ethical dimensions to co-existence. For multiple participants from different backgrounds, stewardship is reimagined as an ongoing relationship, rather than control. This is a concept that resonates with the *Syilx* principle of *siwłk^w* - where water is a relative that sustains life and requires reciprocal care (ONA, 2021).

4. Discussion & Conclusion

4.1 Discussion:

Participatory mapping has long informed environmental decision-making by translating local knowledge into spatial data for land-use planning, conservation, and resource management (Raymond et al., 2009). In ecosystem services (ES) mapping, participants identify areas of ecological, cultural, or provisioning value, often guiding conservation and land-use priorities (Brown & Fagerholm, 2015). ES approaches have influenced the establishment of marine protected areas (Ban et al., 2013), forest-use zoning (Cronkleton et al., 2010), and resource co-management frameworks (Valdivia et al., 2010). ES participatory mapping serves as a tool to mediate local and expert knowledge with institutional decision-making – creating potential for legitimacy, procedural fairness, and accountability (McCall & Minang, 2005).

At the same time, the inclusivity of the ES approach is limited by its anthropocentric nature. Ecological functions are valued primarily for the benefits, such as carbon storage or recreation, they confer to humans (Chan et al., 2016). While effective in cultivating care among policy makers, the utilitarian logic risks flattening ecological complexity and obscuring more-than-human agency (Lorimer, 2012; Whatmore, 2006).

The findings of this research suggest that the value of mapping more-than-human interests lies less in the cartographic product and more in the process. Struggling to spatialize more-than-human interests prompted participants to confront uncertainties pertaining to their ability to know, speak for, and map more-than-human interests. This uncertainty creates opportunities for humility, reflexivity, and a willingness to revise unconscious beliefs – qualities essential to adaptive forms of governance (Folke et al., 2005; Shah & Rodina, 2018). By engaging “untrained experts” alongside scientists, the process expanded and validated a greater range of knowledges (Lorimer & Hodgetts, 2024). This finding extends collaborative environmental governance literature by demonstrating how participatory mapping may support reflexivity and humility through encounters with epistemic limits (Hill et al., 2015).

In practice, mapping more-than-human interests may inform early scoping, value articulation, and reflexive assessment stages of environmental decision-making. That being said, it should be used to compliment, rather than replace, existing tools. Early on, it may support articulating environmental values, negotiating trade-offs between human and non-human interests. During implementation, it could function as a feedback mechanism for identifying socio-ecological

consequences. Post-project, it may support the assessment of impacts on multispecies relationships. Used this way, more-than-human participatory mapping becomes a diagnostic and reflexive tool for adaptive and collaborative stewardship (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Hossu et al., 2018).

Although ES approaches are grounded in utilitarian valuation and more-than-human approaches in relational ethics, they may be complementary if used sequentially and dialogically. ES mapping provides a policy-relevant language for allocating resources and guiding regulation (Costanza et al., 2017), while more-than-human participatory mapping surfaces the relational and ethical dimensions that ES overlooks. Used together, they could bridge quantitative and qualitative environmental assessments. An ES approach could guide resource allocation, while a more-than-human approach contextualizes these choices within multispecies relationships and decenters the human experience. A mixed-methods approach may be key to re-orienting stewardship towards the goal of co-creating thriving multispecies futures.

4.2 Conclusion

This research suggests the potential value of more-than-human participatory mapping to become a relational practice that reshapes how we co-produce environmental knowledge. By inviting participants to try to map with, rather than for, nature, the process created space for them to recognize that human and more-than-human worlds are interdependent. The process cultivates reflexivity, humility, and the ability to confront uncertainty, which may support adaptive and ethical stewardship.

If integrated thoughtfully with ES mapping, more-than-human participatory mapping could offer a means to bridge quantitative assessment and deep qualitative understanding of the environment. Its strength lies in bringing ethical and affective dimensions into dialogue with quantitative observations. Future research should test how this approach can be operationalized within environmental decision-making structures as a precursor to ES mapping, a complement to adaptive stewardship, or simply a tool to reflect on the impacts of environmental decisions.

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6. References

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